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FOCUS ON SELF-DIRECTED LEARNING: THE LEARNING AND ASSESSMENT PHILOSOPHY OF THE UNIVERSITY COLLEGE TWENTE

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ABSTRACT

Background

Developments in modern engineering have led to new materials and production technologies, and as a consequence, new designs that can no longer be attributed to single fields of engineering. Today's breakthrough technologies cross traditional borders between classic fields of engineering and extend to business and social sciences. Innovations emerge from surprising and unpredictable combinations of classic fields, raising questions for engineering curricula. Modern engineering solutions require not only technical but also social perspectives and understanding. They require an integrated socio-technical perspective and an understanding of how technical solutions function in the real world. They require engineers who can identify connections across boundaries between disciplines and see interrelatedness of problems and solutions across different fields. In addition, with changes in the world taking place at an ever-increasing speed, future graduates can no longer rely on their education to be sufficient throughout their career, they will need to update their knowledge and skills continuously.

These developments in turn mean that higher education needs to adapt, with more focus on interdisciplinarity, broader skills (or 21st century skills), flexibility, and learning skills (Goldberg & Sommerville, 2014; Graham, 2018; OECD, 2018; Morris, 2019). Goldberg & Sommerville (2014) even call for educating a whole new engineer.

The ATLAS programme of the University College Twente is educating this new engineer, giving students a broad multidisciplinary project-based education with a combination of natural science/engineering, social science, and mathematics. As teaching philosophy the programme has embraced the concept of self-directed learning (Gibbons, 2002; Saks & Leijen, 2014; Morris, 2019). The individual

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academic development of students lies at the heart of the curriculum. Apart from ensuring an academic foundation, the programme is not based on a specific set of prescribed courses, nor on curriculum requirements, nor on restrictions. ATLAS students are encouraged to explore academic opportunities within and beyond what is offered by the programme.

The students develop their own learning plan with a description of what they want to learn and how, called a Personal Development Plan (PDP). Much is possible, as long as it meets the minimum academic requirements as set out in the general Intended Learning Outcomes of each semester. Students choose their own method of learning, either by following courses offered in the ATLAS programme, courses from other programmes at the University of Twente or other universities, or online. Cooperation is encouraged in all semesters: ranging from groupwork in the semester projects of the first two years, to peer-learning in the theoretical courses. At the end of each semester the students reflect on what they have learned, substantiating their claims with evidence, in their Self Evaluation Report (SER). This SER is the basis for the assessment, and the assessment and feedback on the SER again serve as a source of input for the next PDP. Students are supported in writing their PDP and SER by personal mentors, different workshops on self-directed learning, examples of previous years, and individual feedback.

In this workshop the participants will experience this PDP-SER cycle themselves, and will learn how more focus on self-directed learning can help improve (engineering) education to better prepare graduates for their future work life.

Learning objectives of workshop

In this workshop we will not only explain how the PDP-SER cycle works in the ATLAS programme, but participants will go through their own PDP-SER cycle as well, thus experiencing what this PDP-SER cycle is and how it works. Furthermore, the participants will learn what is needed to implement (parts of) such a system in their own programmes.

Set up of the workshop

At the beginning of the workshop, all participants will write their own Personal Development Plan, to translate the workshop's objectives into personal learning objectives. We will continue with an assignment which lets the participants experience the effect of self-determination in assessment. We will then explain how the PDP-SER cycle works in the ATLAS programme, what we do to make it work for students and discuss our experiences. Next, the participants will work in small groups on applying the lessons from ATLAS to their own programme. To guarantee that participants can learn from one another and at the same time can contribute individually, we would like to have a minimum of 12 and a maximum of 20 participants.

Evaluation of learning results

We'll conclude the session with an evaluation of the findings of the different groups, to share experiences of applying the insights on their own programme. Furthermore

we will reflect on the lessons learned, both as a group as well as individually. For the latter, the participants will write their own SER, which guarantees that they will have concrete lessons to take home, to implement in their next PDP.

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